

Happy New Year! Hello and welcome to the first LNL newsletter of 2025. Let's jump right in. Also look out for exciting new developments in next month's newsletter.

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Funding opportunities

[Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure \(PSDI\) funding call](#)

PSDI are inviting proposals from the community to run events that engage the community on issues around scientific data. They have funding available to run events in the UK running before 31st March 2025, with a smaller pot of money for events beyond that point. **Accepting proposals until 2nd February 2025.**

Examples of events include: knowledge sharing events, workshop / hackathon style events for data sharing or software, workshops to discuss scientific standards, creation of training materials to be incorporated into PSDI. Events are expected to engage with the community (as broadly as possible) and will be expected to write a report to showcase the outputs of the event and how this contributes to the scientific community. **Ideally, events should be co-funded, with 20% of the cost contributed by your organisation or partners.** Proposals will be reviewed by the PSDI team and assessed for their viability and proposed impact. A further call for events will be run for events after 31st March 2025.

UKRN are aware of a few ideas bubbling up to submit to this call. Would you be interested in applying? Our reading of the call suggests that bids will be much stronger if they address a particular topic / challenge, rather than being based at a particular institution. If challenge-based bids come from groups of institutions that includes a **UKRN Open Research Programme (ORP)** partner, the ORP **may be able to provide the 20% match funding.** Please contact ukrn-admin@bristol.ac.uk if you are interested in this opportunity.

Report on the UKRN Replication Games

After months of promoting it, the [UKRN Replication Games](#) finally arrived in December 2024. Over 50 researchers from Bangladesh, China, Denmark, Mexico, Spain, Switzerland and across the UK were involved. Led by Abel Brodeur, Derek Mikola, Juan Aparicio and Bruno Barbarioli from the [Institute for Replication](#) (I4R) the researchers were organized into 15 teams and worked to replicate 13 papers published in *Psychological Science*, *Nature Human Behaviour*, the *American Economic Review* or the *American Journal of Political Science*. You can read more about their experiences [here](#). We hope to continue working with I4R and will keep you updated with developments.

Dorothy Bishop Prize nominations please

There is still time to nominate someone for the Dorothy Bishop Prize. There will be up to three awards. The winners will each be awarded a prize of £500 (in the form of Amazon vouchers) and a “Doscar” (a Lego minifigure of Dorothy Bishop). You can nominate yourself, or nominate another person **with their permission**.

Nominations close at midnight GMT on Sunday 26 January 2025.

The UKRN Dorothy Bishop Prize Task Force will shortlist based on:

- Evidence of a contribution to the promotion and delivery of activities that have served to improve research or promote open scholarship. Contributions will be evaluated relative to opportunity and access to opportunity.
- Alignment with the [mission and values](#) of UKRN.

A task force consisting of members of the UKRN Advisory Committees will evaluate the nominations and create a shortlist. The winner(s) will then be chosen by the Supervisory Board. Nominees will be notified about whether they have been shortlisted in February 2025. The winner or winners will be announced at the UKRN Annual Meeting in March 2025.

Nomination form: <https://tinyurl.com/UKRN-Dorothy-Bishop-Prize-2025>

(clicking on the yes/no radio buttons opens up further pages on the form)

In-person Open Research Sandpit Event

Oxford Brookes University - January 22nd (RSVP needed)

The aim of this one-day event is to bring people together from across the UK Reproducibility Network around the theme of "Open Research at the Early Stage". We will devote the morning to a “Sandpit” where we will share and develop project ideas. After lunch, the afternoon will then be given over to a short Writing Retreat. Relevant inputs

into the Sandpit would include previous proposals (either successful or unsuccessful) in the Open Research space, which could be presented in the form of short talks (15 minutes). This will be accompanied by a collective sourcing of upcoming grant calls related to Open Research, and opinion pieces related to the theme. While the primary focus of the Writing Retreat is likely to be grant development, we might use some of the time to collaboratively creating a position piece for publication. Relevant documents will be shared in advance of the meeting. An RSVP to Joe Corneli jcorneli@brookes.ac.uk is needed both for this purpose, and to set up catering.

9:45AM Coffee available

10AM-1PM Sandpit activities

1PM-2PM Lunch

2PM-3:30PM Writing activities

3:45PM-4PM Introduction to Writers' Workshop format for follow-up and close of the day

Note: The UKRN Community Project will be able to support two bursaries covering travel and accommodation for LNLs who would not otherwise be able to attend. Accordingly, please advise if you would need a bursary to attend. In case of oversubscription, we will ask the UKRN's Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) Advisory Committee for advice on how to award these funds. **Please contact Joe Corneli** for further information.

Job opportunity

Junior Researcher in metaresearch (postdoc)

EXCELSIOR: EXCELlent Science with Impact, Open and Reliable meta-research team
University of Coimbra, Portugal

Closing date: 24 January. If you have a PhD and are interested in metaresearch and research improvement, please consider applying. The position is open to researchers from many fields. Activities may include conducting experimental or observational meta-research studies; developing automated tools to detect common problems and beneficial practices in research publications; implementing and testing interventions to improve research quality and practice; working with different stakeholder groups and local, national and international networks to improve research culture and practice; and providing and evaluating the effectiveness of training in metaresearch or good research practices. This is an exciting opportunity to shape the future of a new metaresearch team in southern Europe.

Please email tracey.weissgerber@uc.pt or excelsior@uc.pt if you have questions or want more information.

LNL Regional groups update

Some LNLs have been meeting up through the regional groups. Please let us know if you do get together. There is some budget available through early 2025 to cover transport and light catering costs. Let us know what you talked about and how these meetings can be useful to the LNL community contact@ukrn.org

Photo credit: Phan Minh Cuong An - Pixabay

Welcomes and goodbyes

Please welcome new LNLs joining UKRN, and thank you to those stepping out of the role to move onto other exciting opportunities! We try to report all changes but if we miss you, please let us know and we will include you in the next newsletter.

Please welcome:

[Chris Kirk](#) - Senior Lecturer in Sport and Exercise at Sheffield Hallam University.

Huge thanks, goodbye and good luck:

Grant Abt, University of Hull

We are currently looking for new LNLs within University of Exeter, University of Gloucestershire, University of Greenwich, and University of Sunderland. If you have relevant contacts there please let us know so we can follow up - contact@ukrn.org

LNL past events - now resources for you

[Project TIER webinar](#)

Last year Richard Ball gave an overview of the Project TIER protocol. He was joined by Aneta Piekut, Senior Lecturer in Quantitative Social Sciences, University of Sheffield. Project TIER uses a consistent directory format, each contains 2 files (a readme file and a report file) and 3 folders (data, scripts, outputs). The protocol is software neutral. There was discussion around how to use the TIER protocol with students. Please feel free to contact Richard at [Project TIER](#) to learn more. If you would like more information on Aneta's syllabus and slides please feel free to [contact her](#).

The [webinar is now available](#) on the [UKRN YouTube channel](#) alongside a host of other UKRN resources.

LNL webinar

[Transparency and Openness Promotion \(TOP\) Guidelines](#)

11th February 2025 1:00 pm – 2:00 pm

[The Transparency and Openness Promotion \(TOP\) Guidelines](#) are a policy framework designed to enhance the verifiability of empirical research claims in research. The Center for Open Science (COS) has recently announced a major update to the TOP Guidelines, effective from January 2025. A preprint introducing the updated TOP framework is available [here](#). The revisions are the result of an extensive consultation process with the TOP Advisory Board, currently chaired by Sean Grant and co-chaired by the [University of Chester LNL Suzanne Stewart](#). Suzanne will be moving up to the chair role for 2025 and this workshop is a great opportunity to learn from your fellow LNL about how this update applies to your own research and how you might use it in your LNL activities. Register [here](#)

UKRN Webinar

[Update on UKRN projects STAR and METEOR/COMET](#)

30th January 1:00 - 3:00

An update on the [STAR \(Sustainable & TrAnsparent Research data\)](#), [METEOR \(METa-research for the Enhancement Of Research culture\)](#) and [COMET](#) research projects. The STAR project assessed the development and implementation of open data policy and practice higher education institutions. METEOR investigated the use of metaresearch evidence in institutional decision-making that affects research culture. Both projects conducted qualitative interviews and focus groups with professional staff at 20 UK universities. While the STAR project is ending, we will also hear about how during 2025 the COMET project will be building on and scaling up the work started by METEOR. Register [here](#)

Speakers: Jess Wheeler, Pen-Yuan Hsing and Amy Devenney, University of Bristol

Conferences

[Qualitative Open Science: Challenges, Opportunities, Tensions, and Synergies](#)

Vrije Universiteit in Amsterdam; 28 March 2025 (some hybrid options)

The one-day event will comprise plenary talks and interactive workshops on a variety of topics related to qualitative Open Science. Participation is free-of-charge and lunch will be provided. Some of the sessions are hybrid. Places are limited, so please do not postpone signing up. Register [here](#).

[Propose a project for the Responsible Research in Action Unconference](#)

Deadline January 26 Do you have an idea for a project to improve research culture and practice? We're looking for leaders who would like to propose and lead a project during

the [RRiA unconference \(September 22-24, 2025 in Berlin\)](#).

Projects may seek to improve any aspect of research culture and practice, including all phases of the research process. Examples may include projects related to open science, responsible research practices, team science, stakeholder engagement in research, diversity, equity and inclusion, research assessment reform, research funding allocation, or scholarly communication. Submissions from early career researchers are encouraged, and you don't need to be a researcher to submit. The unconference is open to other stakeholders, including funders, publishers and editors and administrators.

Reading recommendation

[Practical Routes to Preregistration: A Guide to Enhanced Transparency and Rigour in Neuropsychological Research](#)

Written by the British Neuropsychological Society Open Science Group and colleagues (including University of Stirling LNL [Gemma Learmonth](#)). It is the product of community discussion, a survey, and a BNS symposium. The authors review the balance of rigour and pragmatism needed to make preregistration viable, map out issues and potential solutions, and signpost resources and publication routes. Read more [here](#).

Quokka qualitative coding app

Developed by [William Ngiam](#) at the University of Adelaide, quokka is a free-to-use, in-browser app for qualitative coding. His hope is that it's fairly intuitive and flexible so that it can fit most workflows. There's an app demo [here](#).

And finally...

We are delighted to announce that the Community Project has been granted a no-cost extension to the end of May 2025. The newsletters will continue. If you would like to contribute just get in touch, we would love to hear from you. It's your newsletter! contact@ukrn.org